

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11048808>

EFFICIENT WAYS AND METHODS OF USING CRITICAL THINKING TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *Critical thinking is the ability to pose questions, develop a variety of arguments, and make independent, thoughtful decisions. Therefore, the main idea of using technology is to create such an atmosphere of learning through game techniques, in which students, together with the teacher, actively communicate, consciously reflect on the learning process, monitor, confirm, refute or expand knowledge, new ideas, feelings or opinions about the world around them. And, of course, they do it quite fluently in English. In this article, experience on the use of critical thinking techniques in modern English lessons are concerned.*

Key words: *critical thinking, creative active personality, interaction, challenge, cluster, motivation, understanding, information, development, reflection.*

A teacher is a person who occupies a special place in a student's life, who is the backbone of the school, who creates a rich future. The requirement of today is that a person should possess modern knowledge and technologies, have high qualification and deep experience. It is very important for a teacher that students have a wide range of knowledge, can express their own opinion about the events taking place in any society. Critical thinking will definitely help a learner to develop the abilities we have mentioned and work successfully in any field of science in the future. Critical thinking is a type of learning technology that is given special attention today and is well implemented in our country. The 21st century is the age of the educated, where

information and modern technology are developing and news in the field of science and culture is increasing by the minute. For our country's reputation to be high, its ideals to be clear and its future to be bright, it is necessary to pay attention to students' literacy and language skills. In one course, we tried to master various methods and forms of interest-raising learning. In a course that included dialogic learning, formative assessment, critical thinking, learning and teaching using ICT, the thing that disappointed and impressed me the most was critical thinking. Every child from an early age should be able to think freely, realize their goals, confront obstacles, adapt, etc.

Therefore, it is the duty of every teacher to form students' critical attitude to every question in every lesson, to teach them to speak openly and freely. Critical thinking is a method used to understand, evaluate, analyze and synthesize information gained through observation, experience, concern and judgment, and can also be the basis and motivation for action. Critical thinking often involves a willingness to imagine something, to make alternative decisions, to introduce new or modified ways of thinking and acting, and means a commitment to organized social activities and to encourage others to think critically. The process of critical thinking at the elementary level is: - gathering relevant information; - critically analyzing and evaluating evidence; - guaranteed solutions and concise conclusions; - involves reviewing assumptions and recommendations based on extensive experience.

Along with complex tasks such as critical thinking in teaching and learning, this process involves recognizing uncertain assumptions and values, problems and finding effective means of solving them, understanding the importance of prioritizing different tasks. In critical thinking, the child synthesizes the information he or she needs in his or her brain, then provides examples to make an opinion argumentative, from a point of view, expresses his or her opinion, and when objections arise, tries to give a reasoned response, sticking to his or her position. And all these processes happen in a matter of seconds, if during the lesson critical thinking takes ten to twelve minutes, then there are only one or two minutes per student. And during this period, the ability to collect, synthesize, develop, and speak is accustomed to the student's mastery. Through actions (gestures), nonverbal, verbal techniques, the student convinces other classmates of the correctness of his or her thought. Student can only discover scientific and technological innovations when he or she feels free to think and have an opinion. Critical thinking is usually associated with later stages of education - with students in upper secondary and tertiary education. However, the foundations of critical thinking can be developed early in education to develop the necessary skills while working with young children. The best way to do this is to encourage students to give meaning to the facts of their experiences. We have plenty of examples of ways of life in different parts of the world

and at different times in history that can be used to spark children's interest and develop their critical thinking skills. Critical thinking involves developing skills such as gathering evidence through observation and listening, considering context, and applying appropriate judgment in making decisions. The game focuses on the skills of speaking concisely, not being blocked when expressing an opinion, being specific within established rules, and paying attention to the seriousness of an opinion. During the lesson, the pupil has been thinking in detail and learning from other subjects.

Makes sure the game is coherent and reasoned. Critical thinking promotes not only informed expression of opinion, but also intelligent questioning. If any student is trying to intimidate an opponent, the only way he or she can do so is by asking a question. When a student who asks a question is looking for an answer, the student who answers shares what he or she knows to give an accurate answer. This will pique the interest of the other students and create an atmosphere of critical thinking in the class as a whole. The teacher should not remain neutral either, but should work with the students to express different opinions and motivate them. Let us pay attention to how these stages are realized. First of all, pupils familiarize themselves with the new teaching material (visual aids, clippings, texts and videos related to the lesson). The second stage is understanding.

The period of acquaintance with aphorisms, scientific forecasts, innovations on this topic takes a very big place. Because in order for the child to form an opinion, he must master the topic. Comparing the thoughts and knowledge accumulated in the comparative period, taking into account the opinion of scientists, compares them with his own opinion. The next stage is the summary. At this stage, the student will fully analyze his thoughts, summarize them and move to a specific opinion. The evaluation and application stage is the final stage. The question of how other classmates evaluate, whether there is an opportunity to use this opinion is considered at this final stage. Research on classroom relationships has shown that certain patterns of interaction - exploratory talk, quotation and dialog - not only engage teachers and students in joint action to internalize meaning and knowledge, but also promote intellectual aspects by developing high level thinking.

Visualization and direct interaction with oral media reduces formal learning, allowing children to develop reasoning skills and be educated in individual ways. They protest against traditional methods such as learning through books, so teachers need to reconsider their decisions to guide rather than control the learning and research processes. Consequently, dialog is very important in fostering critical thinking in children. The ability not only to read a text, but also to formulate related questions, answers from other classmates have a great impact on his critical thinking. The teacher's activity is also taken into account. It is important that students ask questions

about the topic or news outside the textbook, answer them with different variants, express their opinion regardless of correctness.

Dialogic learning and critical thinking have been in very close contact with each other. Critical thinking through dialog. (repetition of statements, analyses, classification and categorization, questions related to lexical topics in the lesson) develops various games ("Auction", "Field of Wonders", "Quote", etc.), recalling the topics discussed through the game, discussion at the end of the lesson through dialog between teacher and student, reducing errors and risks, reducing choices, speeding up the "delivery" of concepts and principles through structured, cumulative conversations and discussions achieves mutual understanding. The teacher should concretize the agreement on the rules of dialog, build a model of dialog in the classroom, students should work with each other in finding new and most effective approaches and interacting with collaborative methods of constructing meaning

This requires understanding students' backgrounds and interests and paying attention to their attitudes and emotions. By listening to and analyzing students' actions and statements when responding to them, teachers will be able to provide effective educational support to students. The concept of "learning as assessment" and the principle of formative assessment means not only learning, but also learning through participation in knowledge building methods. Critical learning through dialog is important in a student's life. here we will take Alexander's theory of Dialogic Learning as a basis. If we study the applied study of the classroom according to the theory of dialogic learning, it is doubtful about the model of classroom communication in which the views of students in terms of dialectical and dialectical pedagogy are ignored or perceived insignificantly. Communication with children and direct verbal communication facilitates children to express themselves clearly.

Analysis and results

According to the new professional development program in Kazakhstan, critically thinking teachers can build on the above-mentioned structures and processes of children's critical thinking. But, first of all, we should differentiate the concept of reflective teaching and consider the need for critical thinking in the educational program. Critical thinking is presented as a purposeful, goal-oriented thought process capable of using sound arguments and context, conclusions and methods and criteria. In connection with the development of children's critical thinking, namely reading through listening and research, understanding context and the ability to apply appropriate criteria to make decisions, teachers should develop appropriate methods and technologies to form the theoretical framework, inferences and conclusions necessary to understand the educational program and the learning process.

The critical learning program consists of various strategies. Usually fifteen of them are used in our classes.

They are:

1. Describing the main idea
2. Grouping
3. Writing an essay
4. Edward de Bono's six-caps
5. Bloom's taxonomy
6. Traveling to a gallery
7. Venn diagram
8. Author's chair
9. Bus stop
10. Yes-no
11. Attack of the brain
12. Small and subtle questions
13. Synquain
14. Fishbone
15. I am confident that through the above strategies, success can be achieved.

For interesting daily lessons, the most important thing is that children participate at a high level in the lessons. These strategies are an invaluable asset. And there are strategies such as Black Box, PIM, Ideal, Cluster, Insert and others.

These methods have been practiced, in the future it is believed that these strategies and make sure English lessons are at a high level. In the "thought provoking" strategy, the children learned to write on a given topic, what influenced them, what ideas, what thoughts. In the first lessons, students were guided to expand on the author's idea in later lessons by limiting themselves to just writing about the content. Edward de Bono's Six Hats strategy is useful for Kazakh language learning, especially for the younger class. First, children tend to wear hats (it is important that they are colored), thus creating a positive classroom environment. Once put on, responsibility increases. Demonstrating knowledge gained has a high impact on aspirations for leadership. Secondly, it allows children to relate to the same topic in different ways.

For example, what are the six faces of one fox? What do the students answer to this? - white cap: where does it live; - black cap: what color is its skin; - red cap: what does it eat; - green cap: is it in Kazakhstan; - red cap: Will it live in a zoo or not? - cap: The cap tells others what his differences from the animals are. Here we have seen that only one fox has the opportunity to look at it from different sides and learn more about it. Through a Venn diagram, students compare characters, animals. A deep mastery of qualities, humanity, honesty and other issues can be achieved through this Venn

diagram. The consolidation strategy allows students to think freely, openly explore a topic, and integrate new ideas. This strategy can be accomplished either in a group or in pairs. By grouping students, the following results can be achieved: 1. Come to a common conclusion, i.e. group thinking of students in one question 2. A common interest is formed, cohesion increases 3. All students work because commanders change frequently and weaker students actively respond. 4. Reveals and clearly identifies unclear points of the topic, Knowledge of students working in this group will be productive. Reflective teaching involves critical thinking about what children have learned. It requires learning, recording and evaluating critical thinking skills. These abilities and skills are evident in tasks that require discussion and consideration of certain arguments in the learning process. Thus, they know, for example, about travelers and travel because these people have the opportunity to learn about the relationship between the environment and technology, which affects the consciousness of needs or continuous search in history, as well as the socio-economic development of human beings. Critically thinking learners are active in any environment, subjects. Communicates with other subjects to ask the right question, make a reasoned opinion and discover the meaning. And those students who only think and are closed in one direction are unlikely to be able to make scientific discoveries in the future. In schools of other nationalities, it is difficult to express their opinions freely in Kazakh. But if they always actively attend classes and work hard to master these strategies, they will surely solve this issue as well. Difficult at first, although the lack of vocabulary, improper merging of grammatical persons (suffixes and continuations), and lack of oral practice have had an impact, I can safely say that "even if one does not speak and speak," - gains the ability to think at one's level.

Critical thinking "utilizes a modular lesson consisting of three stages. [1,67]

1. Awakening to the challenge
2. Realization (deciphering, understanding the meaning)
3. Reflection (reflexion) - attention to the mind itself, to its mental state

Invitation

Actualize the learner's past knowledge and experience;

- Activate the activity of learners;
- Formation of motivation (rationale) for learning activities;
- Individualized learning of learners in learning

Goal setting;

- Acquire new knowledge with the learner;
- Knowing the relationship of a feature to a new feature, building understanding and systematizing knowledge;
- Learning how to work with information;

- Supporting the goals set for the enlistment period;

Implementation

INSERT is an effective tool that teaches reading comprehension, guided thinking, and expression. When reading, familiarizing the learner with the topic.

V - "I know."

- "I don't understand."

+ - "New information for me",

? - "I am amazed" with marks.

New methods in English lessons can be demonstrated on the interactive whiteboard. You can also use many approaches to explain the lesson during the presentation. For example, I took the English topic "Sweet Swan of Avon" for the English playwright W. Shakespeare. The following methods can be used here: explaining the lessons, setting the scene, teaching the students. [2,24]

Methods

1. Jigsaw reading
2. Five line poem. (Five line poem)
3. Picture gallery, (Suret gallery)
4. T-table
5. Munsterberg method.

T-table

(T-table), Table 2

William	Anne
William Shakespeare, the greatest English poet and dramatist was born on the 23 rd of April, 1564 in Stratford-on-Avon in Eglan.	She was 8 years older than William. _____ _____ _____

We used this method to talk about the two main characters. This method can be used in order to describe the positive and negative aspects related to the behavior of the characters in the work. Also, the T-table method can be used in two topics or comparing two subjects. For example, this method can be used to learn about the characters in the work and master the good, bad qualities. [3,29]

Picture gallery method.

Let's make a small trip to these places. They are:

1. Shakespeare birth places
2. Anna Hathaway Cottage. (the early home of Shakespeare's wife.)
3. The foundations and gardens of Place. (where Shakespeare died.)
4. Halls croft (the home of his daughter Susannah).

5. Mary Arden’s House (the home of poets mother).

I have used Shakespeare to travel to the places of his life. Through this method, it can be seen that Shakespeare internalized the names of lands more deeply in his childhood, in his life, and in his writing. On the one hand, organizing it as a journey will be interesting for school children as well. Because they learn to go around the classroom, traveling by the names of lands or their images.

Jigsaw reading Methods :

chart 3

was	in the	in Henly	house
born			Shakespeare
Hathaway	that	Shakespeare	married at the
was	Anne	the woman	age of 18

In this method, sentences related to the topic should be arranged in sequence. This promotes the development of the student’s thinking and explores ways to use the interactive whiteboard. Because they think deeply when doing this task, they try to find a solution faster, resulting in a broadening of the student’s horizons.

Five line poem. (Five line poem method:)

Five line poem Methods

**Quick-witted,
hardworking,
friendship**

2 line

3 adjectives

Shakespeare

Kecme4

Poet

1 line noun

Write, play, act

**Better a witty
fool than a foolish wit**

of sentences or proverbs related to the theme
of the fourth line of 3 verbs,

the fifth line consists of a special
impressive word or sentence

Munsterberg’s Method "

There are whole words between many letters. The learner's task is to quickly read and underline these words.

How many words can you create?

- What do I know?
- What have I learned in new ways?
- How has my learning changed?
- What can I do with this knowledge?

Above 1. Jigsaw reading 2. Five line poem. (Five line poem) 3. T-table 4. Using the Munsterberg methods, the learner is given the following opportunities:

- develops knowledge
- finds the results of the problem task,
- discusses the given task, i.e. expands his/her horizons by speaking, sharing with a neighbor, reasoning
- learns new words, enlarges his vocabulary
- comprehension includes new knowledge

Conclusion

The student receives information about new knowledge and acquaints them with the knowledge.

To teach critical thinking, it is necessary to pay attention to the following requirements:

- To teach critical thinking takes time; - Need to give the opportunity to express their opinions openly, not to put any opinions correctly; - Disseminate different thoughts and opinions (from the teacher's side); - Require reasoned speech, expressiveness; - The most important thing is to evaluate the opinion. Using critical thinking, the student: firstly, increases interest, secondly, develops personal abilities, thirdly, is inculcated to express opinions, fourthly, pays attention to accuracy. All in all, this time is the time of knowledge. "In the modern world, the strength of a country is measured, first of all, by the knowledge of its citizens," the head of state said. To open new horizons in any field of science and contribute to the development of our country's future, we must be free in thinking, colorful in language.

Critical thinking is the ability of every individual in any situation to think, examine, generalize and express his/her opinion in a free environment. Critical thinking is one's own, individual thinking. It means asking questions and constantly seeking answers, identifying problems that need to be solved, expressing one's opinion on each issue, proving it, and investigating the accurate consideration of others' opinions and the logic of these proofs.

In conclusion, in the process of oral language learning, the critical thinker is empowered in the following ways. Forms students' communicative competence and finds the results of problem assignments.

Students improve their ability to think critically in English In the process of critical thinking, students will improve their language skills and creativity in oral and written communication with smart active mobility and competitiveness, gaining information about their previous knowledge about new knowledge and supporting them with ancient knowledge.

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